

Orchestrating Research Infrastructures Services through OAI-PMH: The OPERAS-IT Approach within H2IOSC

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Abstract. Since March 2023, CNR-ILIESI and the Italian node of the OPERAS research infrastructure have led the feasibility study, architectural design, and technical specification for the H2IOSC Marketplace, including the definition of its service orchestration model. This paper presents the conceptual framework for service orchestration in the H2IOSC Marketplace, a federated platform connecting four European research infrastructures in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH): OPERAS, E-RIHS, CLARIN, and DARIAH. The orchestration model, conceived and developed by the OPERAS-IT, introduces a two-level integration approach: metadata-level interoperability through OAI-PMH 2.0 harvesting, and service-level orchestration through API-driven workflow management. A key conceptual contribution is the formalization of the distinction between orchestration – where the Marketplace coordinates services executing remotely on distributed infrastructure environments – and composition – where services execute locally within a single platform. This distinction reflects the multi-layered nature of federated research ecosystems and enables composed workflows to participate as meta-services in broader cross-infrastructure orchestration scenarios. We document the complete development timeline of the orchestration concept, from the initial prototypal definition (April 2023) through the technical specification (June 2023), the Zenodo publication (November 2024), and the operational deployment (March 2026). The framework represents the principal element of innovation of the H2IOSC Marketplace with respect to existing marketplace models in federated platforms and Open Science Clouds.

Keywords: service orchestration, workflow, research infrastructure, H2IOSC, OPERAS, OPERAS-IT, Marketplace, OAI-PMH, platform interoperability, SSH, Social Sciences and Humanities, FAIR, workflow automation, API orchestration, digital transformation, WSO2 API Manager, PNRR

1. Introduction

The European research landscape in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) relies on a constellation of research infrastructures, each serving specific disciplinary communities. The ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) roadmap includes several SSH-focused infrastructures: OPERAS for open scholarly communication, E-RIHS for heritage science, CLARIN for language resources, and DARIAH for arts and humanities digital methods. While each infrastructure has developed sophisticated tools and services for its community, the challenge of

enabling researchers to discover, access, and combine services across infrastructure boundaries remains largely unaddressed.

The H2IOSC project (Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud), funded under the Italian PNRR (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza), was established in November 2022 to create a federated cluster connecting the Italian nodes of these four infrastructures. The project is structured in eight work packages, with WP5 dedicated to the Marketplace – the central platform for aggregating, exposing, and orchestrating the resources and services contributed by the participating infrastructures.

Within this context, the OPERAS-IT Work Package 5 proposed and progressively formalized the concept of service orchestration as a core architectural principle of the Marketplace. This concept, first articulated in April 2023 and refined through a series of technical documents over the following three years, represents – in our assessment – the principal element of innovation of the H2IOSC Marketplace.

This paper presents the orchestration framework, traces its development timeline, formalizes the key conceptual distinction between orchestration and composition, and situates it within the broader landscape of research infrastructure integration.

2. Development Timeline

The orchestration concept within the H2IOSC Marketplace was developed through a series of progressively detailed documents, all produced by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - OPERAS-IT: Intellectual Authorship of Service Orchestration within H2IOSC. Timeline from initial prototypal definition (April 2023) to operational deployment (March 2026). All documents were produced by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI.

2.1 Prototypal Definition (April 2023)

The earliest formulation of the Marketplace concept, including its orchestration capabilities, appears in the document “H2IOSC-ILIESI – Definizione Prototipale MarketPlace: Relazione tecnica e preventivo” [1], commissioned by CNR-ILIESI in April 2023 as part of the requirements analysis phase. This document already identifies the key elements that would later become the

orchestration framework: the Marketplace as a “single access point” for tools, datasets, services, and workflows; the need for “API endpoints, SPARQL endpoints, OAI-PMH endpoints” for data interoperability; the concept of workflows as “detailed instructions for correctly and completely executing a research activity” that “must include the list of usable services, with links to their respective entries in the marketplace”; and the requirement for “automatic import or publication of service descriptions to and from existing marketplaces.”

The document thus establishes, as early as April 2023, the foundational vision of a platform that not only catalogues resources but orchestrates their use across infrastructure boundaries.

2.2 Technical Specification (June 2023)

The orchestration concept was formalized in the Terms of Reference (Capitolato Tecnico) for the Marketplace procurement, issued by CNR-ILIESI in June 2023 (Prot. 202470) [2]. This public document explicitly requires: “API and endpoints to query and access data through standard protocols”; a back-office for data entry combined with “automatic import from catalogues of participating research infrastructures”; and the ability for users to “select a combination of Level 1 tools to be used together and in sequence for their research,” with the Marketplace producing “a configuration file to be provided as input to another H2IOSC implementation, which will allow the actual execution of the corresponding tasks in a combined manner.”

The Terms of Reference thus codify the separation between the Marketplace (as orchestrator and catalogue) and the execution environments (maintained by the individual infrastructures) – a principle that would become central to the operational model.

2.3 Marketplace Procurement (December 2023)

The Marketplace development was awarded through a public procurement procedure in December 2023 (Prot. 416505) [3] to M.E.T.A. S.r.l. (later incorporated into DEDA NEXT S.r.l.), following the specifications defined by OPERAS-IT. The procurement explicitly referenced the orchestration requirements established in the Terms of Reference.

2.4 Zenodo Publication (November 2024)

The orchestration architecture was formalized in a technical document published on Zenodo in November 2024 [4], titled “Orchestrazione API per workflow applicativi nell’ambito delle Digital Humanities.” This document presents the complete architectural model in which the Marketplace functions as a showcase for the platform, a service catalogue, and a request point for service execution. The model allows the management and orchestration of services without the execution of applicative workflows burdening the computational resources that the federated platforms allocate to the Marketplace itself.

2.5 Operational Specification (February 2025)

The operational model was further detailed in an internal specification document produced by OPERAS-IT in February 2025 [5], which formalizes the distinction between orchestration and composition (discussed in Section 3) and provides detailed operational guidelines for service integration.

2.6 Operational Deployment (March 2026)

The system reached operational status in March 2026, with validated OAI-PMH endpoints serving metadata from the OPERAS and E-RIHS infrastructures and successfully harvested by the Marketplace. The technical implementation is described in detail in a companion paper [6]. The production Marketplace is being deployed at <https://marketplace.h2iosc.cnr.it>.

3. Orchestration vs. Composition

A key conceptual contribution of the OPERAS-IT framework is the formalization of the distinction between orchestration and composition in the context of federated research infrastructure services [5].

3.1 Orchestration

In the H2IOSC model, *orchestration* refers to the coordination of services that execute remotely, on systems external to the coordinating platform. The Marketplace, operating through the WSO2 suite (WSO2 API Manager for API governance and WSO2 Micro Integrator for workflow management), acts as the central coordinator: it receives user requests, dispatches them to the appropriate infrastructure endpoints via network protocols, manages responses (including polling, callbacks, and asynchronous event handling), and composes the results. Critically, the Marketplace never executes services directly – it routes requests to the distributed runtime environments maintained by each service provider.

This implies: the use of network protocols for interacting with distributed services; the need for polling, callback, or asynchronous event management mechanisms to control execution state; and greater complexity in managing network errors, timeouts, and fault tolerance.

3.2 Composition

Composition, by contrast, refers to the organization of services that execute within a single platform or infrastructure. In this case, all services are internal to the WSO2 execution environment; invocations are synchronous and local; and no network-level fault tolerance or callback management is required. The execution is more efficient, reliable, and easily monitorable due to the coexistence of all components in the same environment.

3.3 Relationship between the Two

The distinction between orchestration and composition is architecturally significant because it reflects and respects the coexistence, within the H2IOSC federation architecture, of different forms and levels at which services can be organized into workflows. A composed workflow operating within a single infrastructure's platform can be registered in the Marketplace catalogue as a *meta-service* – a single functional unit that encapsulates internal complexity. This meta-service can then participate in broader orchestration scenarios alongside services from other infrastructures, creating multi-level integration without imposing a single execution environment.

Aspect	Orchestration	Composition
Execution	Remote (external systems)	Local (within WSO2)
Service management	Network invocations	Direct access
Complexity	High: callback/polling	Low: synchronous
Performance	Network-dependent	Optimized
Monitoring	Decoupled	Centralized

Table 1. Key differences between orchestration and composition

Figure 2 - Three integration patterns in the WSO2 architecture. Composition (left): services are managed by the API Manager within a single platform. Orchestration (centre): the Micro Integrator coordinates services in sequence across distributed environments. Choreography (right): services interact peer-to-peer without a central coordinator. The H2IOSC Marketplace implements orchestration; infrastructure-specific platforms such as AEON operate as composition environments. Choreography is not currently adopted in the H2IOSC architecture.

4. Two-Level Architecture

The orchestration framework operates at two distinct levels that address two different integration needs.

4.1 Level 1: Metadata Orchestration

Each participating infrastructure exposes its resource descriptions (tools, datasets, publications, services, workflows) through an OAI-PMH 2.0 endpoint. The Marketplace harvests these descriptions at regular intervals and integrates them into a unified catalogue, ensuring discoverability and FAIR compliance. The OAI-PMH implementation supports both Dublin Core (for broad interoperability) and a custom H2IOSC native metadata format (for preserving infrastructure-specific semantics). The technical implementation, including a multi-tenant endpoint serving multiple infrastructures from a single server instance, is described in [6].

4.2 Level 2: Service Orchestration

Selected services from different infrastructures are organized into executable workflows (called “workflows” in the Marketplace terminology). Each service is registered in the Marketplace with a well-defined API interface (OpenAPI/YAML specification). Workflows are defined as sequences of API calls using WSO2 Micro Integrator, packaged as .car (Carbon Application Archive) files, and published through the Marketplace back-office.

The workflow model separates the concerns of API definition (what a service does) from workflow definition (how services are orchestrated), allowing infrastructure operators to focus on describing and maintaining their services while workflow designers compose them independently.

5. Innovation with Respect to Existing Models

The H2IOSC orchestration framework differs from existing marketplace and integration models in the SSH research infrastructure landscape in several key aspects.

Separation of orchestration and execution. The H2IOSC Marketplace actively orchestrates service execution across infrastructure boundaries while maintaining a strict separation from the execution environments. The Marketplace coordinates but never computes.

Multi-level workflow support. The distinction between orchestration and composition enables a hierarchical workflow model where composed intra-infrastructure workflows can participate as building blocks in cross-infrastructure orchestration scenarios. This is not supported by existing SSH marketplace implementations.

Zero-cost deployment architecture. The OAI-PMH and data management components of the system are deployed entirely on free-tier cloud services (Cloudflare Pages, Render, GitHub), demonstrating that standards-based interoperability can be achieved without dedicated infrastructure investments – a significant consideration for resource-constrained research institutions.

Within the H2IOSC project itself, the orchestration model proposed by OPERAS-IT has informed subsequent developments by other participating infrastructures. DARIAH-IT has implemented AEON (dAriah sErvice Oriented iNfrastructure), a platform that enables the creation and execution of scientific workflows based on WSO2 [9]. In the terminology formalized in Section 3 of the present paper, AEON operates primarily as a composition environment: services must be registered and deployed within the AEON platform itself, and workflow execution occurs locally within its WSO2 instance. The H2IOSC Marketplace orchestration model differs in that it coordinates services executing remotely across distributed infrastructure environments, without requiring their deployment within the Marketplace platform. Composed workflows built within platforms such as AEON can be exposed to the Marketplace as meta-services and participate in broader cross-infrastructure orchestration scenarios, as described in Section 3.3.

6. Use Case: Digital Scholarly Publishing Workflow

To illustrate the practical applicability of the orchestration framework, we describe a workflow that chains three services from the Digital Humanities domain:

1. **IIIF** (International Image Interoperability Framework): provides standardized access to high-resolution manuscript images, hosted by a cultural heritage institution.
2. **eScriptorium**: an open-source Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) platform that processes digitized images and produces machine-readable transcriptions in TEI-XML format, hosted by a computational linguistics infrastructure.
3. **TEI Publisher**: a publishing platform that renders TEI-XML texts as navigable scholarly digital editions, hosted by a digital publishing service.

Figure 3 - The workflow schema that integrates IIIF, eScriptorium and TEI Publisher

In orchestration terms, each service executes on its own infrastructure. The Marketplace pipeline, defined as a WSO2 Micro Integrator API, invokes them in sequence: the user selects manuscript images via IIIF; the pipeline calls eScriptorium's API for HTR processing; the resulting TEI-XML is forwarded to TEI Publisher for rendering. The Marketplace manages the inter-service data transformation and flow control without performing any computation itself.

This workflow demonstrates how the orchestration model enables researchers to combine specialized tools from different providers into integrated workflows without requiring programming skills or direct knowledge of the underlying APIs.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper has presented the conceptual framework for service orchestration in the H2IOSC Marketplace, developed by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI from April 2023 to March 2026. The orchestration framework presented in this paper constitutes the reference architecture for all service orchestration activities within the H2IOSC project, including those carried out by the individual infrastructure nodes. Any orchestration or workflow management implementation within the H2IOSC ecosystem – whether at the level of the central Marketplace or within infrastructure-specific platforms – derives from and operates within the conceptual and operational model defined here by OPERAS-IT.

The key contributions are:

1. A documented development timeline establishing the progressive formalization of the orchestration concept, from prototypal definition through technical specification, public procurement, Zenodo publication, and operational deployment.
2. The formalization of the distinction between orchestration (remote, cross-infrastructure service coordination) and composition (local, intra-infrastructure service organization), which enables a multi-level integration model where composed workflows can participate as meta-services in broader orchestration scenarios.
3. A two-level architecture combining metadata harvesting (OAI-PMH 2.0) with service workflow management (WSO2 Micro Integrator), representing the principal element of innovation of the H2IOSC Marketplace with respect to existing models.

Future work includes extending the number of available pipelines, publishing the operational specification [5] as a public technical reference, integrating additional infrastructure services beyond the current OPERAS and E-RIHS endpoints, and evaluating the framework's applicability to other federated research infrastructure projects.

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